

Oxidation of Aliphatic Ketones by Ditellurato Argentate(III) in Alkaline Medium—A Kinetic Study

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Kinetics of oxidation of acetone, methyl ethyl, methyl *n*-propyl, methyl iso-propyl and methyl *t*-butyl ketones by ditellurato argentate(III) in alkaline medium was investigated. The kinetic data and product analysis indicate that only the keto form of the substrate takes part in these reactions. A suitable mechanism consistent with the observed rate law is postulated. Taft equation was found to be applicable for the series with $\rho^* = 3.00$.

THE mechanism of oxidation of ketones using various oxidants has been the subject of study by several workers. Two different views on the form of ketone (keto or enol) involved in the reaction have been expressed. Since the relative rates of enolization and oxidation were the same in oxidations by Cr(VI)¹ and ferricyanide² it was suggested that these oxidants attack the enol form. In the case of peroxy-diphosphate-ketone reaction in acid medium³ and periodate-ketone reaction in alkaline medium⁴, the rate of oxidation was found to be very much greater than that of enolization. It was therefore concluded that in these reactions the attack is on the keto form. In view of this it was thought worthwhile to investigate which one of the tautomers is involved in the reaction during the oxidation of aliphatic ketones by ditellurato argentate(III).

The chemicals used were of AR grade and purified wherever necessary. Ditellurato argentate(III) (DTA) solution was prepared and estimated as reported earlier⁴. The progress of reaction was followed spectrophotometrically by finding the absorbance of Ag(III) solutions at 395 nm. Stoichiometric studies revealed the reactions to be of 1 : 1 type. Under the experimental conditions the main product identified was acetic acid.

Under the conditions $[Ag(III)] \ll [ketone]$, a plot of $\log(\text{absorbance})$ vs time was linear indicating the order in $[Ag(III)]$ to be unity. From the slopes of such plots the pseudo-first order rate constants (k') were calculated. The plot of $\log k'$ vs $\log [ketone]$ was also found to be linear in each case indicating the order in $[ketone]$ to be also unity. The rate of oxidation was found to increase with an increase in $[OH^-]$ and decreased with an increase in $[tellurate]$. For instance, in the reaction with acetone at constant $[Ag(III)]$, $[acetone]$ and temperature (304K) the rate constant increased from $1.34 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$ to $3.28 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$ when $[OH^-]$ was increased from $3.00 \times 10^{-2} M$ to $6.00 \times 10^{-2} M$. Under the same conditions at constant $[OH^-]$ the rate constant

decreased from $2.97 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$ to $0.900 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$ when $[tellurate]$ was increased from $7.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ to $25.0 \times 10^{-4} M$.

No free radicals were detected in these reactions. The bimolecular rate constants for these oxidation reactions (Table 1) are very high (10^8 to 10^4 times) when compared with the corresponding enolization rates of the ketones^{6,7} under the same experimental conditions. We therefore assume the keto form to be the reactive species in the case of all the ketones studied. The probable mechanism of oxidation appears to be :

Equilibria (1) and (2) are written in the light of the arguments reported in our earlier paper⁴. The rate law for the above scheme comes out to be

$$\frac{-d[Ag(III)]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_s [Ag(III)] [RCOCH_3] [OH^-]}{[(H_3TeO_6)^{3-}]}$$

which explains well all the kinetic data obtained.

It can be seen from Table 1 that the order of reactivity is acetone > methyl ethyl ketone > methyl *n*-propyl ketone > methyl iso-propyl ketone > methyl *t*-butyl ketone, which is also the order of ketone content. This points out a probable attack on the ketonic form by Ag(III) and supports the view that the oxidation does not involve electron transfer from the enolic form though the medium is basic. The same trend of reactivity was reported by Panigrahi *et al*⁸ in the oxidation of aliphatic ketones

TABLE I—BIMOLECULAR RATE CONSTANTS FOR Ag^{+} -KETONE REACTION

	Acetone	methyl ethyl ketone	methyl <i>n</i> -propyl ketone	methyl iso-propyl ketone	methyl ter-butyl ketone
k'' at 304°K $dm^3mol^{-1}min^{-1}$	1.76	0.888	0.460	0.360	0.215

by periodate in alkaline medium. Taft's plot of $\log k/k_0$ vs σ^* was found to be linear (correlation coefficient=0.997) with a slope, $\rho^*=3.00$. The positive value of ρ^* suggests an electron-rich transition state and therefore the reaction rate must decrease with the electron releasing capacity of the groups as can be seen from the k'' values in Table I.

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